

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ДЛЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ НАВЫКОВ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА**Кульмагамбетова С.С***Западно-Казахстанский университет имени Махамбета Утемисова,
кандидат педагогических наук, доцент***Рафалова Р.И.***Западно-Казахстанский университет имени Махамбета Утемисова, Уральск***Аблайкызы А.***Западно-Казахстанский университет имени Махамбета Утемисова, Уральск***MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS****Kulmagambetova S.,***Mahambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University,
Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor***Rafalova R.,***Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk***Ablaikyzy A.***Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk***Аннотация**

В данной статье рассматривается использование современных образовательных технологий для развития критического мышления при обучении английскому языку как один из способов повышения их мотивации. Способность студентов к критическому мышлению позволяет расширить их общее поле через развитие, в процессе работы с новой информацией решать такие задачи, как анализ, экспертиза, отбор необходимого материала, оценка себя и своего дела.

Abstract

This article examines the use of modern educational technology for critical thinking in English language teaching as one way of increasing their motivation. Students' ability to think critically allows them to expand their general field through development, in the process of working with new information to solve problems such as analysis, examination, selection of necessary material, evaluation of themselves and their case.

Ключевые слова: Современные технологии, критическое мышление, рефлексия, технология, Интернет

Keywords: New technology, critical thinking, reflection, technology, Internet.

Over the past 10 years there has been a growing interest in foreign languages due to the positive changes in all spheres of society, including the establishment of new relations with the countries of the world community within the framework of foreign language education. XXI century in the formation of a comprehensive intelligent, talented individuals, the problem of education in the centre of the state's attention task to enter into the World Education Space for optimal influence on the development of education and science, the further democratization of education, the possibility of harmonization of education in accordance with modern requirements and place new demands on the whole methodological system.

As an active subject of intercultural communication, modern educational technologies are needed to solve the task of training competent specialists of a new formation, providing a high level of mutual understanding and interaction in the context of international relations. In this connection, one of the urgent problems in the modern system of school education is the formation of students' critical thinking in writing and reading.

Philosophically, psychologically, pedagogically, we prefer to highlight a number of foreign scholars engaged in the study of this problem, among them: Edward de Bono, J. Dewey, M. Lipman, D. Halpern, D. Clouster, R. H. Johnson, P. Freire, J. Steele, C. Meredith, C. Temple. Among Russian scientists V.A. Bolotov, A.V. Korzhuev, G.B. Sorina, D.M. Shakirova, L.I. Shragina and others have been widely advocating the necessity and possibilities of developing critical thinking skills of students and teachers in educational process.

An examination of the works by the abovementioned authors does not yet give a clear-cut definition of the critical thinking process.

The majority of definitions of critical thinking are based on an intelligent, differentiated attitude to making complex decisions about values and actions. R. Ennis defines critical thinking as "making considered decisions about what to do and what to believe" [1].

American philosopher and educator J.Dewey believes that critical thinking occurs only when students are faced with a particular problem. "The basic question

that is asked in connection with a situation or phenomenon will be from what problems this phenomenon arises" [2].

J. Dewey describes critical thinking as the tendency of the human mind to process incoming information in order to understand stuck ideas, generate new ideas or solve different problems [3].

To summarize, critical thinking is at the heart of students' acquisition of reflexive and evaluative skills. This activity is defined in the sciences of philosophy, pedagogy and psychology as a special type of human activity, originating from birth, constantly developing, having a vital importance. It is very important to define the basic concepts that allow us to designate the skills of critical thinking. They are reflexion-criticism-self-criticism-argumentation-evaluation-self-evaluation-valuation [4].

Based on the analysis of the above-mentioned concepts, we have identified the skills that allow us to experimentally implement critical thinking skills.

The concept of reflection first appeared in philosophy and was considered to be reflection on things in the mind of the individual. Reflection (Latin for reflect - to turn back) is a person's tendency to internal mental acts and postures, to self-cognition. It is emphasized by L.S. Vygotsky that cognition and the role of reflection as its constituent [5] are formed only in the process of self-knowledge. That is, reflection consists in forcing a human mind to concentrate on itself, to become aware of its actions and understand, on the basis of what rules and tables these actions operate. The purpose of reflection is to identify, comprehend, remember the main components of an activity, such as meaning, types, techniques, problems, ways of solving them, the result obtained, interaction of students, interaction of students with the teacher, attitude towards the activity.

Criticism and criticality - the ability to independently defend one's beliefs and find answers to opposing views; the ability to analyse new information. Criticality is based on 'evaluation' as well as dialectical thinking. It means the scientific application of scientific methods, principles and rules of logic.

Although self-criticism is directly related to criticism, it has the following features: self-assessment from correction with critical assessment, self-assessment and the ability to analyse evidence in correction consist of skills and form qualities such as resourcefulness, curiosity, insight, discretion, courage, morality in the individual.

Assessment and self-evaluation and self-assessment and comparing the action plan, goals and objectives and the final result Analysis of the cause-and-effect relations of one's own faults and compatibility, and the ability to make decisions aimed at eliminating faults in performance.

Judgment about pricing-a set of actions to clarify, summarize, contrast one's own and others' opinions.

Although people have a strong desire to criticise themselves, a lack of the necessary business skills and the skill to apply this knowledge in practice can lead to criticism. The difference between criticism and self-criticism is the proper communication of thought in terms of logic.

The need for students to develop critical thinking is an issue of spontaneity in this ability that concerns many scholars and educators. Of course, critical thinking is moulded by the logic of human life and depends on personal qualities, the social environment and upbringing. Formation of critical thinking should be one of the advanced tasks for teachers in the 21st century. At present teachers do not pay enough attention to the ways of thinking formation and learning technology.

Formation of critical thinking is a purposeful development of intellectual skills of students and teaching cognitive search processes. Based on the goal of developing critical thinking, R.V. Pohl believes that understanding the significance and correctness of students' own judgments and value orientations is an awareness of their own natural predisposition [6].

The ability to shape and teach communicative and critical thinking determines the level of professional competence of a teacher. The teacher's success in teaching critical thinking, the ability to understand new information correctly, to remember it, and to analyse it depends directly on the students' productive activities. Thus, critical thinking is an integral part of a teacher's professional qualification. This is due to the fact that this type of thinking is unique in its social value, fully manifested in solving group problems in public debates.

Now we have decided to focus on modern educational technologies with practical value, aimed at shaping students' critical thinking skills. The notion of "educational technology" becomes an important structural unit of pedagogical work. Modern educational technologies are unified approaches to achieve the intended goal, an ordered system of activities. Conscious application of scientifically grounded educational technologies is the most important condition for obtaining new information [7]. A set of operations for the practical and theoretical understanding of objective reality. To apply the necessary technology in a specific situation, it is necessary to determine the subject or object of the direction of pedagogical impact, what the result and how to achieve it. Three levels of classification are known, determining the role and place of educational technology:

At the subjective level, it is justified by the subject's own opinion and decision in the application of the educational technology. The subject of activity is as follows: specialists (they use external methods of action, influence and interaction), the person himself (independent work, independent actions), the specialist or the person on whom the pedagogical influence is created (combined actions of the specialist and the person himself).

Defines the way modern technology is implemented at the subject level. Each technology has its own subject environment, reflecting a certain way of its implementation, the functionality of the technology. They include a group of practical methods-exercises, trainer's tasks, games, etc.; a group of educational impact technologies - persuasion, information technologies; a group of educational organization technologies - management technologies, control technologies, technology for creating a situational environment; a group

of stimulation technologies - methods of encouragement, methods of persuasion, control methods.

We decided to give an example of application of a number of effective educational technologies of teaching and writing, reflected in the works of foreign and domestic scientists, aimed at forming critical thinking skills of schoolchildren, as well as our experience of teaching, in the process of training foreign language specialists.

Let's consider as an example the technology of developing critical thinking in written language on the basis of authentic material as well as the lesson model, which uses interactive methodology of foreign language teaching. This lesson is designed specifically for secondary school students on one of the topical issues of the education system - the topic of "Home Education". Students of the predicted group have a sufficient level of skills and knowledge to work on the basis of the interactive format, the use of Internet resources and the creation of presentations with a slide show. The students' personal qualities and ability to work in groups and pairs were taken into account when designing the tasks. The session is aimed at working with professionally oriented authentic texts by pupils, analyzing and analysing information, critical assessment as well as increasing the level of motivation.

The main techniques used in the lesson are from the title of the article, predicting the value of the information conveyed, brainstorming, conceptual table, thematic association, debate, critical assessment of oneself and one's actions.

The lesson is divided into learning phases. Discussion of a question on a given text at the end of the lesson. Homework-Creation of a computer presentation using Internet resources.

Thus, the application of modern educational technologies for critical thinking in the process of teaching English is one of the ways to increase their motivation. This is due to the fact that students' ability to think critically allows them to expand their general field through development, in the process of working with new information to solve such tasks as analysis, examination, selection of necessary material, evaluation of themselves and their work.

References

1. Dewey J. (1916). *Education and Democracy*. - New York: Macmillan. - P.
2. Dewey How we think: Restatement of the relation of reflective thinking to the educational process. - Boston: D.C. Heath, 1933. - P. 530.
3. Paul R.W. *Critical Thinking*. - Ohio State University, 1990. - P.
4. Shakirova D.M., Sigbatullina I.F., Suleymanov D.S. *Thinking, Intellect, Giftedness: Problems of Theory and Technology* / Ed. by M.I. Makhmutov. - Kazan: Center for Innovative Technologies,
5. Vygotsky L. S. *Dynamics and Structure of the Adolescent Personality: Cross. on Age and Educational Psychology*. - M.: Pedagogica, 1982. - c. 138-142.
6. *Pedagogy and Psychology: The Explanatory Dictionary of Tax Terms in the Kazakh Language* / Ed. by A. A. Baskskiy. A. Ku-sayynov. - Almaty: School, 2002. - C. 256.